

An unexpected guest in the winter: first record of *Aradus bimaculatus* Reuter, 1872 (Hemiptera: Aradidae) for the Balkan fauna

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Abstract: The first record of *Aradus bimaculatus* Reuter, 1872 in Bulgaria and on the Balkan Peninsula is reported with data on the habitats and the true bug assemblage in the region during the collection period (end of February – end of March).

Keywords: Aradidae, Bulgaria, flat bugs, Heteroptera, new records, winter activity

Introduction

Up to now, the flat bug fauna of Bulgaria comprises four genera and a total of 25 species (Josifov, 1986; Heiss, 2001; Simov, 2005; Heiss, 2006). In the period February–March 2021 the insect activity was investigated, as a part of the study of the winter diet of bats in the Iskar Gorge, Bulgaria. During the survey, a single specimen of an unknown small flat-bug was collected from a trap. The specimen was identified by the first author as species of *Aradus bimaculatus* Reuter, 1872. In this paper, we present data about the first record of this flat bug species in Bulgaria.

Material and methods

The winter activity of the insect communities in the investigated area was monitored using flight interception traps (FIT) with a collecting surface of 0.15m² and modification of the bottom subunit as suggested in Basset (1988) (Fig. 1). From the last week of February until the end of March 2021, we deployed twelve flight inter-

ception traps. They were set on the slopes of Iskar Gorge in different habitat types and at different altitudes above sea level. Exact localities, the main habitat types around the traps, and the tree species on which each trap was deployed are given in the Table 1. The traps were positioned at mid-level in the crowns, at about 7–9 m above the ground. Using a 9 m telescopic rod, each trap was surveyed once every 10 to 14 days. Both collectors were filled with a collecting fluid (propylene glycol (C₃H₈O₂), which has a low evaporation coefficient.

The material is deposited in the National Museum of Natural History, Sofia (SOFM) collections.

Results and discussion

Aradidae

Aradus bimaculatus Reuter, 1872

Material examined: Bulgaria: Iskar Gorge, Lakatnishki Skali protected site, Lakatnik railroad station,

Table 1. Fight interception traps in the studied area in Lakatnishki Skali Protected Area, Iskar Gorge.

Trap number	Decimal geographic coordinates		Altitude	EUNIS Habitat types	Tree species
	N	E			
1	43.08805	23.38756	384 m	T1-2116 Dacio-Moesian ash-alder forests T1-1112 Eastern European poplar-willow forests	<i>Juglans regia</i>
2	43.08790	23.38845	384 m	T1-2116 Dacio-Moesian ash-alder forests T1-1112 Eastern European poplar-willow forests	<i>Alnus glutinosa</i>
3	43.08828	23.38840	390 m	T1-2116 Dacio-Moesian ash-alder forests	<i>Fraxinus excelsior</i>
4	43.08834	23.38761	392 m	T1-9B8 Sub-Mediterranean and Pannonic mixed forests H3.2A13 Balkan Range calcicolous chasmophyte communities	<i>Quercus</i> sp.
5	43.08858	23.38500	406 m	H3.2A13 Balkan Range calcicolous chasmophyte communities H3.2E Bare limestone inland cliffs	<i>Prunus domestica</i>
6	43.08846	23.38291	408 m	H3.2A13 Balkan Range calcicolous chasmophyte communities H3.2E Bare limestone inland cliffs T1-9B8 Sub-Mediterranean and Pannonic mixed forests T1-1112 Eastern European poplar-willow forests	<i>Juglans regia</i>
7	43.09120	23.38520	671 m	T3-M2 Native pine plantations	<i>Pinus sylvestris</i>
8	43.09159	23.38290	633 m	T1-9B222 Moesian oriental hornbeam forests	<i>Carpinus orientalis</i>
9	43.08906	23.38168	530 m	H3.2A13 Balkan Range calcicolous chasmophyte communities T1-9B8 Sub-Mediterranean and Pannonic mixed forests	<i>Quercus</i> sp.
10	43.08923	23.38209	530 m	H3.2A13 Balkan Range calcicolous chasmophyte communities T1-9B8 Sub-Mediterranean and Pannonic mixed forests	<i>Quercus</i> sp.
11	43.09005	23.38510	570 m	H3.2A13 Balkan Range calcicolous chasmophyte communities H3.2E Bare limestone inland cliffs	<i>Robinia pseudoacacia</i>
12	43.09040	23.38606	608 m	H3.2A13 Balkan Range calcicolous chasmophyte communities H3.2E Bare limestone inland cliffs T1-9B8 Sub-Mediterranean and Pannonic mixed forests	<i>Fraxinus excelsior</i>

43.08906°N; 23.38290°E; 530 m a.s.l.: 1 ♀ (Fig. 2), 23.ii–5.iii. 2021, flight interception trap on *Carpinus orientalis*, M. Langourov, N. Simov leg., N. Simov det. (SOFM).

This record increase the number of flat bug species known from Bulgaria to 26 species. The range of *Aradus bimaculatus* includes predominantly territories of Northeastern and Central Europe and Central Asia: Andorra, Austria, Czech Republic, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Poland, Russia, Slovakia, Spain, Sweden, Ukraine, Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan (Heiss, 2001; Aukema et al., 2013).

This is the first record of *Aradus bimaculatus* for the fauna of Bulgaria and the Balkans. The closest published localities of the species are situated north of the Carpathian massif and it is also recorded at high altitudes in the mountains in some Mediterranean countries. This new record potentially presents the range expansion of the species to Southeastern Europe and the Eastern Mediterranean. On the other hand, *A. bimaculatus* could be a very rare species in its southern range and easily overlooked in previous studies due to a lack of suitable conditions or the usage of unsuitable trapping techniques, as is the situation with other newly

Fig. 1. Flight interception trap in the studied area.

Fig. 2. *Aradus bimaculatus* Reuter, 1872, female.

Fig. 3. Data of the collection periods of *A. bimaculatus* in the Heteroptera collection of the Zoological Institute of the Russian Academy of Sciences.

established flat bug species in Central Europe (Gossner et al., 2018).

Data on the phenology and flight activity of *A. bimaculatus* are very scarce (Heiss & Péricart, 2007). Palaearctic *Aradus* species actively migrate during the spring and the beginning of the summer (Kiritschenko, 1913, 1951, 1957; Stark, 1933). Our analysis, of the material of *A. bimaculatus* stored at the Zoological Institute, Russian Academy of Sciences (the largest collection of *A. bimaculatus*), indicates that most of the specimens are sampled from the end of the spring and early summer (Fig 3). Considering the latest tendency for milder winters, particularly at high latitudes (Twardosz et al., 2021) and the well-documented shift towards earlier dates in insect spring phenology (Cohen et al., 2018), our record is not a surprise. As those shifts can potentially alter the patterns of species interactions, more research is needed.

Based on a single specimen record in the FIT, we could only speculate about the host trees of *A. bimaculatus* in Bulgaria. Most probably it could be the oriental hornbeam (*Carpinus orientalis*) – the most common tree species in the studied plot. The Moesian oriental hornbeam forests (EUNIS habitat T1-9B222) are typical for the Iskar Gorge.

Other species of true bugs recorded during our study in the same habitats follow.

Miridae

Deraeocoris (Camptobrochis) serenus (Douglas & Scott, 1868)

Material examined: Bulgaria: Iskar Gorge, Lakatnishki Skali protected site, Lakatnik railroad station: FIT 2, 1 ♀, 23.ii–5.iii. 2021, M. Langourov, N. Simov leg., N. Simov det. (SOFM); FIT 6, 3 ♂♂, 1 ♀, 23.ii–5.iii. 2021, M. Langourov, N. Simov leg., N. Simov det. (SOFM), 2 ♂♂, 5–26.iii. 2021, M. Langourov, N. Simov leg., N. Simov det. (SOFM); FIT 9, 1 ♂, 5–26.iii. 2021, M. Langourov, N. Simov leg., N. Simov det. (SOFM).

Lygus rugulipennis Poppius, 1911

Material examined: Bulgaria: Iskar Gorge, Lakatnishki Skali protected site, Lakatnik railroad station: FIT 9, 1

♂, 5–26.iii. 2021, M. Langourov, N. Simov leg., N. Simov det. (SOFM).

Anthocoridae

Anthocoris nemoralis (Fabricius, 1794)

Material examined: Bulgaria: Iskar Gorge, Lakatnishki Skali protected site, Lakatnik railroad station: FIT 5, 1 ♀, 23.ii–5.iii. 2021, M. Langourov, N. Simov leg., N. Simov det. (SOFM).

Anthocoris sp.

Material examined: Bulgaria: Iskar Gorge, Lakatnishki Skali protected site, Lakatnik railroad station: FIT 2, 1 ♀, 23.ii–5.iii. 2021, M. Langourov, N. Simov leg., N. Simov det. (SOFM).

Orius (Heterorius) majusculus (Reuter, 1879)

Material examined: Bulgaria: Iskar Gorge, Lakatnishki Skali protected site, Lakatnik railroad station: FIT 2, 1 ♀, 23.ii–5.iii. 2021, M. Langourov, N. Simov leg., N. Simov det. (SOFM); FIT 5, 2 ♀♀, 23.ii–5.iii. 2021, M. Langourov, N. Simov leg., N. Simov det. (SOFM).

The results of this study suggest that regular collections during the warmer days in the winter in different habitats could provide information about the dispersal ability and flight activity of many true bug species. Indirectly, these studies would also give an indication of the likely speed of response of Heteroptera to past and ongoing climate change and provide insights into the dynamics of local fauna.

Acknowledgments

Funding for this study was provided by the Bulgarian National Science Fund (project CP-06-COST/15 from 16.12.2020). We also would like to acknowledge funding from the EU Framework Horizon 2020 through the COST Action CA18107 ‘Climate change and bats: from science to conservation – ClimBats’ (<https://climbats.eu/>). The first author is most grateful to Fedor Konstantinov for the help with some

Russian literature sources and for the collaboration during visits in the Entomological collection of the Zoological Institute, St. Petersburg, Russia.

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